

Devechi Lowland and the Qusar Sloping Plain.” Baku, 2015.

8. <https://osmanemin.wordpress.com/2018/02/17/az%С9%99rbaycan-fiziki-cografi-rayonlari-yeni/>

9. <https://eco.gov.az/>

10. <https://gsaz.az>

Normatov I. Sh., Hojiev A.E.

Tajik National University, Dushanbe, Tajikistan, e-mail:inomnor@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15455874>

DROUGHT DYNAMICS IN THE VALLEY OF RASHT DISTRICT (TAJIKISTAN) UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE CONDITIONS

Abstract. The dynamics of the Standardised precipitation index and the Standardised precipitation and evapotranspiration index in Rasht district for the period 1950-2023 is characterised by a constant trend. The results of studies of meteorological conditions of Lakhsh district for the period 1961- 2021 to identify the possibility of drought occurrence are presented. The trend of the drought indices shows an increase in humidity over the period 1961-2021. Despite the positive trend in humidity over the period considered, extreme and severe droughts of varying duration have been observed.

Keywords: drought, Rasht, precipitation, temperature, SPI, SPEI, correlation

ДИНАМИКА ЗАСУХИ В ДОЛИНЕ РАШТСКОГО РАЙОНА (ТАДЖИКИСТАН) В УСЛОВИЯХ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ КЛИМАТА

Аннотация. Динамика стандартизированного индекса осадков и стандартизированного индекса осадков и эвапотранспирации в Рахтском районе за период 1950-2023 гг. характеризуется постоянным трендом. Представлены результаты исследований метеорологических условий Лахшского района за период 1961- 2021 гг. с целью выявления возможности возникновения засухи. Тенденция изменения индексов засухи показывает увеличение влажности за период 1961-2021 гг. За рассмотренный период несмотря на положительную тенденцию изменения влажности наблюдаются экстремальные и сильные засухи различной продолжительности.

Ключевые слова: засуха, Рахт, осадки, температура, SPI, SPEI, корреляция

Introduction. Drought one of the manifestations of emergencies is a serious problem for Central Asia. Experts estimate that more than 70 percent of the region's territory is considered vulnerable to natural disasters. Droughts are less frequent than floods but affect more people. Over the past decade droughts have affected 60 per cent of the population exposed to extreme weather events. Droughts are expected to become more frequent in Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan due to prognoses temperature increases and longer periods of extreme heat and evaporation in areas with less precipitation [1, 2].

Continued glacier melt and reduced snow cover will exacerbate water resource problems in Central Asia. In addition, high temperatures and intense precipitation will lead to more frequent and intense natural disasters such as droughts, heat waves, floods, landslides, mudslides and avalanches [4].

Materials and Methods. The present work is devoted to monitoring the occurrence of drought in Rasht of the Rasht valley of Tajikistan due to meteorological conditions in the period 1961-2023.

The climate of the Rasht valley depends on its altitude. The altitude creates a valley rich in biodiversity with several agro-ecological zones. Since the beginning of the 20th Century, there has been a steady increase in average temperature of 0.07°C and a change in precipitation trends. Winter precipitation is steadily increasing, while average spring precipitation has remained stable. The meteorological conditions in Rasht district monitoring by use of data from Rasht (39°05'00"N, 70°30'00"E) meteorological station were used.

Results and Discussion. Seasonal distribution of mean annual temperature and precipitation in Rasht district is shown in Figure 1. Fig. 1 shows that the maximum values of temperature and precipitation in Rasht district are observed in summer and spring, respectively, with the peculiarity that, unlike other geographical latitudes, the temperature is kept within moderate limits with abundant precipitation in spring. The observed climatic conditions are considered favorable for the cultivation of a wide range of agricultural products.

The change in temperature and precipitation for a period of more than 50 years in the Rasht district, as can be seen in Fig. 2, is characterised by an almost constant trend, which is probably related to the location of the valley, surrounded by high mountain areas of the Karategin, Zeravshan and Alai ridges that belong to the Alai mountain system, and to the south on the left bank - the Peter the First ridge that is part of the Pamir-Darvaz mountain system.

Fig.1. Seasonal distribution of temperature and precipitation in Rasht district

Figure 3 shows the results of SPI and SPEI calculations for the Rasht district based on meteorological data from the Rasht meteorological station, which show an almost constant value of the trend of the indices for the period 1950-2023. From Fig. 3 it can be concluded that the dynamics of the Standardised precipitation index and the Standardized precipitation and evapotranspiration index in Rasht district for the period 1950 - 2023 is characterised by a constant trend. In other words, it can be assumed that with the observed trend of meteorological conditions for the period 1950-2020, the probability of drought in Rasht district is negligible.

Fig.3. Dynamics of SPI6 and SPEI 6 for Rasht district for the period 1950 - 2023

The duration of droughts in each of the decades of the considered period in the Rasht region, shown in Fig. 4, shows that the occurrence of droughts in a certain selected geographical area does not have a certain regularity, but is determined by a certain combination of meteorological parameters of this area, the most important of which is the amount of precipitation and temperature.

The comparison of SPEI with SPI is important to identify the role of potential evapotranspiration (PET) in the occurrence of a significant difference between the indices.

As the difference between SPEI and SPI is normally distributed, the standard deviation $\Delta(\text{SPEI}-\text{SPI})$ is used to quantify the variability of SPEI and SPI index values. When plotted over time, the standard deviation shows that the models are again clustered according to their radiation term, with the differences between SPEI and SPI remaining constant over the year [5].

The inclusion of potential evapotranspiration (PET) leads to a noticeable difference in the index values, confirming that SPEI is a significantly different drought index from SPI. The largest differences between SPEI and SPI are observed in summer, when PET accounts for most of the climatic water balance. SPEI is most sensitive to the radiation term of PET, and therefore SPEI is recommended as an alternative to SPI for quantifying anomalies in the accumulated climatic water balance that includes potential evapotranspiration.

“Иқлим ўзгариши шароитида гидрологик тадқиқотларнинг асосий йўналишлари:
замонавий ёндашувлар ва технологиялар”

Fig. 4. Duration of extreme and severe droughts in months in each decade of the period 1950-2023 in Rasht district

Figure 5 shows the difference between the Standardised Precipitation and Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) and the Standardised Precipitation Index (SPI).

Fig.5. Long-term monthly of SPI, SPEI and their differences in Rasht district

Fig. 5 shows that the difference between SPEI and SPI is minimal in the winter and spring periods, and maximum in the summer period. SPEI is an important and useful tool for comparing meteorological droughts, as it takes into account the temperature regime as a factor leading to evapotranspiration in addition to precipitation. The inclusion of PET makes a noticeable difference in the index values, confirming that SPEI is a significantly different drought index to SPI. The largest differences between SPEI and SPI are observed in summer, when PET accounts for most of the climatic water balance.

In order to establish the relationship between the standardized drought indices and the meteorological conditions of Rasht district, the long-term monthly averages of precipitation and temperature were compared with the climatic norms of the area shown in Fig.6 (a, b).

As can be seen from Fig. 6(a), the average monthly temperature of the southern Tajik lowlands is significantly above the average monthly climatic norms in all seasons. This is naturally reflected in the values of the drought indices and negative values of SPI and SPEI dominate almost throughout the year. A similar picture is observed in the dynamics of changes in the monthly mean values of atmospheric precipitation (Fig.6, b).

It should be noted that the effects of climate change on drought behavior are not only explained by the increase in global temperature, but also by changes in precipitation trends.

Fig. 6. Long-term monthly of temperature (a) and precipitation (b) in Rasht district to relation to climatic norms of temperature and precipitation

Conclusions. It has been established that the main factors determining the processes of migration and precipitation of heavy metals are the acid-base and oxidation-reduction conditions of the aquatic environment.

References

1. Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change / T.F. Stocker, D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J. Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex and P.M. Midgley (eds.). Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA. 2013.-1535p. www.climatechange2013.org/report/full-report/.
2. Second National Communication of the Republic of Tajikistan under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. Dushanbe. 2008. - 93p. www.meteo.tj.
3. Second National Communication of the Republic of Uzbekistan under the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change. Uzhydromet. 2008. http://unfccc.int/national_reports/non-annex_i_natcom/items/10124.php.
4. Study on Drought Assessment and Monitoring Models in Central Asia. Centre for Disaster Management and Risk Reduction of the Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific. 2020. - 57p. www.unece.org.
5. Nogués-Bravo, D., Araujo, M.B., Errea, M.P., Martínez-Rica, J.P. Exposure of global mountain systems to climate warming during the 21st century // Global Environmental Change. 2007. V. 17. P. 420-428.

Muradova Rahida

Baku State University, Baku, Azerbaijan
info@bsu.edu.az/cografiya@bsu.edu.az

THE IMPACT OF CLIMATIC FACTORS ON DENUDATION AND ACCUMULATION PROCESSES IN THE LESSER CAUCASUS

Abstract. *The Lesser Caucasus, one of the most complex mountainous systems of Azerbaijan, stands out with its diverse geomorphological and climatic conditions. This diversity allows for a clearer observation of the influence of climatic factors on the dynamic development of the relief. Climate components such as temperature, precipitation, frost-thaw events, and wind directly affect the scale and nature of denudation and accumulation processes. This study analyzes the mechanisms through which climatic factors influence geomorphological processes in the Lesser Caucasus and investigates the outcomes and practical significance of these interactions.*

Keywords: *Lesser Caucasus, climate, denudation, accumulation, geomorphological processes, temperature, precipitation, frost-thaw, relief*